

CAN YOU HEAR THE EARTH BREATHING? TRANSLATION AND DISCLOSURE IN SOUND ART DATA SONIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

Lacey introduces the concept of disclosure in sound art meaning the sounds that are taken for granted and making them focus of attention [1]. The many technical and artistic choices made during data sonification and performance are not usually made visible to the audience. This paper presents a reflection on the concept of disclosure in sonification sound art performance - ‘Can you hear the earth breathing?’ performed in Berlin in July 2022. The performance included both sonified data representing different elements of the CO₂ system along with field recordings. Design and performance of the work included multiple methods of disclosing technical and artistic choices.

We reflect on our intentions with disclosure, how we put that into practice, and how we might further such practices in the future. We close by proposing new research directions including questions such as how might sonification choices impact the affect of a sound art performance? Does disclosure help or hinder public engagement with the work? And what techniques might we use – practically and aesthetically – to disclose our sonification choices

1. INTRODUCTION

Lacey introduces the concept of disclosure in sound art in terms of taking the sounds that are taken for granted and making them focus of attention. Lacey notes “disclosure is the approach that demonstrates the soundscape always exceeds perceptive capacity, and that beyond the dominant affective forces that shape everyday experience, there are hidden qualities waiting to be revealed” [1, p.166]. These qualities are also hidden inside soundscape recordings, sound art performances, and especially in sonification. Choices are made about how and when to record, how to edit into a piece, what processing and effects are applied, how “raw” data is turned into pitch, gate, velocity, timbre and which instruments are employed to play back the sounds; everything that happens, in Sterna’s term, “before sound” [2]. However, these many technical and artistic

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¹ See <https://www.drusnoise.com/can-you-hear-the-earth-breathing> for video documentation of the performance

choices are not usually made visible to the audience. This paper presents a reflection on an attempt to embed disclosure into the artistic performance of a sound art data sonification piece – our intentions, our thoughts on how well our intentions were met, and thoughts for future performances.

This paper builds on experiences in designing and performing a sustainability focused sound art performance ‘Can you hear the earth breathing?’ in Berlin in July 2022¹. This work attempted to bring to life sustainability cycles and the natural (and un-natural) systems that lie beneath the production and absorption of carbon dioxide – key elements of energy production and consumption. The performance included both sonified data representing different elements of the CO₂ system along with field recordings. Design and performance of the work included multiple methods of disclosing technical and artistic choices. First, the event program included a ‘Cast of Characters’ that presented the system elements, sources of data used for sonification, along with sound and field recording sources. In addition, the program included detail on sound processing, playback instruments, and the tools and processes used to harness/employ/highlight feedback processes between system elements and sound. Second, the sound performance was supplemented with video that mixes footage of CO₂ sources and sinks, “technical” slides and screenshots that illustrated the scaffolding and “disclose” the behind the scenes data, sonification, and sonic choices made. These choices were illustrated with video, screenshots, and screen captures that show the process of data download and manipulation, exporting to MIDI, importing into Ableton, sound design, and processing. Each of these processes contain choices that influence the sound that is heard by the audience; challenging the conception what the audience really hearing.

2. APPROACHES TO SONIFICATION DISCLOSURE

Much has been written on aesthetics and preferences in sonification practices [3], but there is relatively little about the impact of revealing or hiding these choices from listeners. Coming from outside the sonification field, Demers notes that “many hip-hop DJs and artists view sampling as a means of insider communication with their fans, a way

of conveying messages to the select few informed enough to identify quotations [4, p.54]. Sterna takes a deep self-investigation into the role of technologies, spaces, and the artist in her work. Referring to the piece *Currents* installed at the Oslo Opera, she remarks that:

whilst the work's contextual ambition and its relation to the environment were also fully articulated via textual information, this does not mean that the work acted as a representation of the scientific data or that the text was a representation of the work. In this sense, the information about the work that was accessible on site in the Oslo Opera should also be considered an affective body with a capacity to affect, to establish new affective connections, and thus found new transversal machines in complicity with the work's body and the multiplicity of bodies of visitors who together were establishing new affective relations [2, p.158].

It is these 'new affective relations' that are worthy of further exploration in sonification and sound art studies.

Sonification choices have been mapped along various spectra and frameworks such as *Ars Musica* by Vickers and Hogg [5] and indexality from Keefe et al. [6]. Rather than focusing on the relative merits of sonification choices, this paper explores how those choices can be made transparent to listeners and audiences. While there are several ways to engage with these choices, this work is grounded in the theoretical concept of disclosure - taking the sounds that are taken for granted and making them focus of attention. Lacey notes that this approach "reveals the complexity of the urban environment, which is typically hidden by the dominating sounds of the everyday" [1, p.166] And further that "disclosure is the approach that demonstrates the soundscape always exceeds perceptive capacity, and that beyond the dominant affective forces that shape everyday experience, there are hidden qualities waiting to be revealed" [ibid]. These qualities are also hidden inside soundscape recordings and especially in sonification. However, these many technical and artistic choices are not usually made visible to the audience.

Disclosure also applies to the methods used to plan, prepare, and perform this work such as sound processing (including choices made for sonification) and playback instruments, tools and processes used to highlight feedback loops between system elements and sound, and the process of data download and manipulation, exporting to MIDI, importing into Ableton, sound design, and processing. Each of these processes contain choices that influence the sound that is heard by the audience

3. EXPERIENCES FROM CAN YOU HEAR THE EARTH BREATHING?

3.1 Performance details

The breath is one of the most fundamental, most personal, parts of any living being. Mauss notes that "man's first and

most natural technical object, and at the same time technical means, is his body" [9, p.13]. In the 1950s, Charles Keeling started measuring CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere at the Moana Loa Observatory. These measurements showed for the first time how the planet itself is breathing as forests in the Northern hemisphere grow leaves in the Spring absorbing CO₂, then release it back into the atmosphere in the Fall when leaves drop off the trees. The data also shows the accelerating rise of CO₂ in the atmosphere over time. The Scripps Observatory makes available this global CO₂ concentration data. The data is available in time slices from one week to 800,000 years. Data back to 1958 is from the Moana Loa Observatory, further back the data is taken from analyzing ice cores.

This performance included both sonified data representing different elements of the CO₂ system along with field recordings (see Figures 1 and 2). Sounds are performed with modular synthesizers, samplers, biofeedback pads connected to plants, FX pedals, and feedback. The sound performance is supplemented with video that mixes footage of CO₂ sources and sinks, "technical" slides and screenshots that illustrate the scaffolding and "disclose" the behind the scenes data, sonification, and sonic choices made, and video that shows changes over time such as time lapse video of a forest changing over a year and CO₂ data animations.

Figure 1: Live performance in Berlin July 2022. Photo: Lisa Knolle used with permission

Through sonification processes in collaboration with Data Artist Lisa Knolle, we translate each of the raw CO₂ data sets into MIDI. The curves make for some strangely discordant arpeggios. And the MIDI data can also be used to modulate and change the sounds over time. But the measurement of CO₂ is just the end product. CO₂ is produced by (generally) manmade processes such as fossil fuel production and use, industry, transportation, and many forms of human activity. CO₂ is absorbed by plants and oceans which are in turn affected by the sun in the form of solar radiation.

Figure 2: Live performance in Berlin July 2022. Photo: Lisa Knolle used with permission

While described here as discrete elements, in reality, these are all part of interconnected systems and feedback loops [10,11]. These systems are working at nested scales ranging from the microscopic, to the personal, the local, city, region, and global, ranging in time scales from the current moment to 800k years ago and into an uncertain future(s).

3.2 Sonification Process

3.2.1 Data sourcing and analysis

Data was sourced through the Keeling Curve website which collects multiple data record sets from different research sources and data collection methods. Data is available in several time series ranging from daily to the last 800,000 years [12]. Data from 1958 to present was measured at the Moana Loa observatory while pre-historic data is measured from ice core analysis. The different data sources and time scales also had different measurement periods. Recent data is available in regular, predictable 15 minute or daily increments. Older data includes measurements at unpredictable intervals ranging from 100 to over 500 years between data points.

3.2.2 Translation to MIDI

Once the data was downloaded, additional choices were made on MIDI translation. Decisions on upper and lower note bounds, note lengths and note velocity were standardized across time scale data. This meant that while the resulting MIDI file for 800k years was longer than the file for one year, it was not 800k times longer! Data points were from the different time scale data sets were standardized at 1/16 note length. Pitch was standardized with a range of MIDI note values 24 - 100 (C0 - C7) with the lowest recorded CO₂ value at 24 and the highest at 100. Note velocity (loudness) was scaled between a range of 0 - 127 using the same values as pitch. The data was then run through a conversion process using Python to generate a set of 10 MIDI files representing the different time scales of data available.

3.2.3 Playback and Recording

MIDI files were then playing back from Ableton Live through various modular synthesizers to generate different sounds with a range of timbres as loops. In addition, the two and 100k year MIDI files were slowed down so the audio recordings extended over 20 minutes. Recordings were made of “clean” audio along with versions with effects and modulations coming from houseplants connected via TENS Sensor Cable to the modular system. Pads of this cable, placed at two separate areas on the plant, measure the changes in surface conductance to generate control voltage and gate signals that are used for modulating sounds (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: TENS Sensor pads on plant leaves. Photo by author

3.2.4 Composition and Arrangement

An early decision was made to create a composition with multiple themes in roughly historical order. The themes were Water, Plants (both that absorb CO₂), Animals, Industry, and Traffic (producing CO₂). Field recordings representing the themes were arranged on a timeline reflecting the roughly 30 minutes allocated to the performance. Recorded loops were then placed on the arrangement timeline. The initial concept was to arrange the time-scale recordings in chronological order. However, after first experimenting with the recordings, we noted this would result in approximately 29 minutes of drone or slowly changing notes followed by a rapidly rising arpeggio in the final seconds of the performance. The choice was made to instead layer multiple time scale recordings rather than a strict chronological order, in effect changing the indexality balance of the sonification. The final arrangement was exported as 7 x 30-minute tracks that were loaded into the Octatrack sampler for live playback.

3.3 Live performance

The live performance instruments included a Soma Lyra-8 synthesizer, modular synthesizer with voices, effects, MIDI file playback, and clock dividers, houseplant connected to the Instruo Scion module via biofeedback pads, FX pedals (looper, delay, and reverb), mixer, and

MIDI/CV controller (see Figure 4). The performance started by playing a sine wave at 419Hz representing the CO₂ concentration level of 419.1 ppm measured that day. The pre-recorded arrangement of loops and field recordings played from the Octatrack. Throughout the performance, different MIDI files were played back triggering different modular synthesizer voices and (using the clock dividers) at different playback rates. Pre-recorded and improvised sounds were processed through FX pedals.

Table 1 provides a complete list of sound sources and playback methods. Note that this information was provided to audiences as described in the following section on Disclosure Methods.

System element	Data source	Sound source	Processing	Playback Instrument
CO ₂ Concentration levels (today)	Scripps Observatory		CO ₂ ppm converted to Hz	Sine wave through modular synthesizer and Soma Lyra 8
Breath		Field recordings	Time stretch and looped	Octatrack
CO ₂ Concentration levels (historical)	Scripps Observatory		Convert data to MIDI, stretch/normalize time scales. Send MIDI to modular synthesizers	Octatrack playing recorded loops Live modular synthesizers
Water		Field recordings		Octatrack
Plants		Field recordings	Time stretch and looped	Octatrack
Solar radiation	Earth/local magnetic field			Soma Synths Ether
Plants	Plant on table		Convert electricity resistance to pitch, gate, modulation with Instruo Scion	Modular synthesizers
Industrial activity		Field recordings		Octatrack
Transportation		Field recordings		Octatrack
Inter-connected systems			Feedback loops	Mixer, Soma Cosmos looping pedal, Erica Synths Zen Delay

Table 1: Cast of characters (in order of appearance). From exhibition text provided to attendees 22 & 23 July 2022

Figure 4: Live performance gear setup. Photo: Lisa Knolle

3.4 Disclosure process

We took two paths towards disclosure for the performance. First was utilizing photo and video documentation of the sonification process (see Figures 5 and 6). The video included photos of early design sketches, video capture of data manipulation and translation processes, audio recording, and arrangement. While the video clips were not long or detailed enough to show the audience every aspect of our choices, we attempted to communicate that *some* choices had been made even though we were not clear about the impacts of those choices. The video also included footage representing the themes (e.g. ocean and waves for the Water theme, city streetscapes and in-car video for the Traffic) theme.

Figure 5: Background video showing CO₂ concentration data from Mauna Loa. Photo: Lisa Knolle

Figure 6: Example of 'thematic' video in background.
Photo: Lisa Knolle

In addition, we created a two-page information sheet given to audience members at the venue. This information sheet described (in brief detail) the aims of the composition, the sonification process, and the technical and aesthetic choices made (see Figure 7 in Appendix 1). We also included a table that listed the 'cast of characters' in the composition including the data or field recording source, processing applied, and instruments used to play back the data or field recording (see Table 1 above)

3.5 Audience experience

As this was the first performance of the piece, we were not able to capture audience experience in a robust and statistically valid format. Anecdotal feedback was mostly positive with a few notable exceptions. Two attendees commented that the sounds (they had not paid attention to the video) made them feel very anxious. Another attendee commented that the video was 'competing' for attention and found it difficult to both listen to the sound art performance and watch the video at the same time.

4. DISCUSSION AND REFLECTION

The premiere performance of 'Can you hear the Earth breathing?' and this paper raise more questions than answers. We attempted through this piece to both provide a different way of engaging with climate change data and to disclose the sonification process to the audience.

Rather than present quantitative data, here we reflect on the disclosure choices made. The video documentation and overall presentation was well received by audiences and formed an integral part of the artistic experience. However, the video was attempting to both convey data sonification process details and convey the underlying sustainability message through footage of forests, oceans, traffic, etc. Instead of conveying both messages, the video in fact may have done neither. The disclosure process was presented 'free floating' in that the video content was not labelled or directly tied to the sound art performance. This was a deliberate choice to avoid becoming a lecture video but may have undercut our goals. In addition, the content of the video was visually stimulating and engaging – a good

thing! – but also drew audience attention away from the sound. Audiences questioned whether this was a video presentation with accompanying audio or a sound art performance with supporting visuals. Artistically this is not a binary choice but the reminder of the split attention of audiences was valuable. In future performances, we will attempt to more closely link the visual and sound so that audiences will (or might?) be able to more clearly see and hear the relationship between what is happening on screen to what is being performed. Another approach is to leverage the power of live coding. In this approach, the data manipulation and translation would be performed live and projected on screen before the data is played back through synthesizers. This would bring the data sonification *process* itself into the performance and make the data-sound link clear to the audience.

The text handout was a more direct explanation of the sonification and performance process. Audiences attending sound art performances are accustomed to reading an artist statement or program description, so the handout fit within that context. We question how much the technical description contributed to the disclosure process or served more as a technical guide. Future options for the text disclosure might be to format more closely to, for example, an orchestral program which is organized into movements that highlight performers/vocalists for each, often including text of what the vocalists are singing. This would provide a more clear and direct explanation of the data-sound connection. However, as we discuss further below, asking audiences to read text during a sound art and video performance may distance the audience even further.

4.1 Open questions

The experience of the performance and our reflections lead us to a series of open questions that were not resolved in our exploration. Open questions can be clustered into three broad categories. First is around knowledge and understanding – did our disclosure processes help audiences understand the context of the piece and the sonification process itself? The underlying assumptions of this question (i.e. that audiences should understand the context and meaning of an artistic work) is of course one that has been questioned for many years. In a sustainability context, we may also question the value and efficacy of art as simply another instrumental communication tool [13,14].

Second is the effect of such disclosures on the aesthetic experience. To what extent is disclosure part of the artistic experience? Does disclosure impact the wonder and experience of an audience? Audience members and installation attendees arrive with wildly different understandings and expectations of the artistic work. An analogy might be an orchestral performance where some attendees may only know the title of work performed, others may read every page of the program, while others may bring along their own copy of the score to follow along. We wish to explore the balance between disclosure and maintaining engagement with the artistic work.

Third is returning to Sterna's suggestion that disclosure may serve a role in "establishing new affective relations" between the audience, the work, and the space. However, how and why this may happen is the biggest open question that we will continue to explore through future projects and accompanying research.

4.2 Areas of further research

Further research will be valuable for the open questions discussed above. In addition, it would be fruitful to explore differing methods of disclosure. These can range from the typical wall mounted information found in galleries and installation spaces all over the world, to more detailed information sheets, artist talks, project web sites and documentation videos. Of particular interest is how disclosure might become part of the performance or installation itself (through audio, video, text or integration of all of the above) with the potential to take on not just a communicative role but an aesthetically engaging one. It would also be of interest to study the impact of when disclosures are made to the audience. For example, disclosing the context and sonification process before (for example by an artist talk or lecture), during (through the practices we have described), or after (e.g. with a post-show artist talk, audience Q&A, or dialogue session) a performance may have very different impacts on an audience.

5. CONCLUSIONS

'Can you hear the Earth breathing?' was an experiment in sonification of climate data. More importantly perhaps, the piece was an experiment in disclosure of data sonification processes. In challenging the seeming simple question of "what does climate change sound like?", we hoped to spark a different affective relationship with the audience that experienced the performance.

As we note, the performance – and our reflection – has raised more questions than answers. However, we hope that this paper will spark further discussion within the sound art and data sonification communities. We also hope to encourage further exploration of the challenges and opportunities of disclosure in sound art data sonification.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

First in acknowledgement must be the work of Data Artist Lisa Knolle who took on the task of sourcing, analyzing and translating the climate data into MIDI and also captured documentary photos of the performance. Steve Burnside from Alive.BLN provided video production and documentation. We are grateful to faculty and students at the Berlin School of Sound 'Practice-Based Sound Studies for Installation and Performance' course for feedback on early development of the sound art performance and review of an early draft of this paper. We are also grateful to ACUD Macht Neu in Berlin for providing space for the premiere performance of 'Can you hear the Earth breathing?' and to everyone who attended.

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8. APPENDIX 1

Breaths / LP / Deaths

Can you hear the Earth breathing?

Performance (30 minutes) at ACUD Macht Neu 22 & 23.07.22 20.0-23.00
by Steve Williams (drusnoise)

'Can you hear the Earth breathing?' brings to life sustainability cycles and the natural (and unnatural) systems that lie beneath the production and absorption of carbon dioxide. In the 1950s, Charles Keeling started measuring CO2 concentrations in the atmosphere at the Moana Loa Observatory. These measurements showed for the first time how the planet itself is breathing as forests in the Northern hemisphere grow leaves in the Spring absorbing CO2, then release it back into the atmosphere in the Fall when leaves drop off the trees. This performance includes both sonified data representing different elements of the CO2 system along with field recordings. Sounds are performed with modular synthesizers, samplers, biofeedback pads connected to plants, FX pedals, and looping feedback. The sound performance is supplemented with video that mixes footage of CO2 sources and sinks, "technical" slides and screenshots that illustrate the scaffolding and "disclose" the behind the scenes data, sonification, and sonic choices made, and video that shows changes over time such as time lapse video of a forest changing over a year and CO2 data animations.

The core of this work is grounded in the concept of *disclosure* - taking the sounds that are taken for granted and making them focus of attention. Lacey notes that this approach "reveals the complexity of the urban environment, which is typically hidden by the dominating sounds of the everyday" (2017, p. 166). And further that "disclosure is the approach that demonstrates the soundscape always exceeds perceptive capacity, and that beyond the dominant affective forces that shape everyday experience, there are hidden qualities waiting to be revealed" (ibid). These qualities are also hidden inside soundscape recordings and especially in sonification. Choices are made about how and when to record, how to edit into a piece, what processing and effects are applied, how "raw" data is turned into pitch, gate, velocity, timbre and which instruments are employed to play back the sounds.

Disclosure also applies to the methods used to plan, prepare, and perform this work. Here I present the system elements (i.e. primary components of natural systems that produce and absorb CO2), sources of data used for sonification, sound and field recording sources. In addition, I detail sound processing (including choices made for sonification) and playback instruments. In addition, I describe tools and processes used to harness/employ/highlight feedback processes between system elements and sound. Note that there are feedback loops and implications within recording, processing, and playback too. These choices are be illustrated with video, screenshots, and screen captures that show the process of data download and manipulation, exporting to MIDI, importing into Ableton, sound design, and processing. Each of these processes contain choices that influence the sound that is heard by the audience.

Conception, recording, production, performance: Steve Williams/drusnoise

Data artist: Lisa Knolle (@lets.learn.machines)

Data source: C. D. Keeling, S. C. Piper, R. B. Bacastow, M. Wahlen, T. P. Whorf, M. Heimann, and H. A. Meijer. Exchanges of atmospheric CO2 and 13CO2 with the terrestrial biosphere and oceans from 1978 to 2000. I. Global aspects, SIO Reference Series, No. 01-06, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, San Diego, 88 pages, 2001.

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Figure 7: Text provided to audience for performances in Berlin 22 & 23 July 2022